

A SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC EXPLORATION OF CONSUMERS IN A COMPONENT CITY IN CAGAYAN

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Abstract

The socio-economic status includes the aspects of a person's quality of life as well as the possibilities and advantages that are available to them in society. It includes not just money but also financial standing, educational attainment, and different conceptions of social class and position. It is important to all fields of behavioral and social research, including education, since it is a reliable and consistent predictor of a wide range of outcomes throughout the course of a person's lifetime. The goal of this study was to ascertain the socioeconomic makeup of the customers. The questionnaire was the primary tool employed in this study's descriptive-normative data collection strategy. According to a National Economic Development Authority bulletin, the majority of respondents' family monthly income is below the poverty line, their family size is below the average family size in the Philippines, which is 4 to 6 members, and from the various significant sectors under study, the majority of the consumers. In light of the aforementioned findings, the researcher highly recommends that future studies be carried out to ascertain new variables and utilize more respondents in order to enhance the findings while utilizing additional crucial variables to ascertain the socio-demographic status of the respondents that would enhance the results.

Keywords: Socio-Demographic, Exploration, Consumers, Affiliation, Social Research, Social Class

INTRODUCTION

The socioeconomic situation of a person encompasses their level of living as well as the opportunities and benefits they have access to in society. Along with money, it also takes into account one's financial situation, level of education, and other perspectives on social class and position. Since it is a trustworthy and consistent predictor of a wide range of outcomes throughout a person's lifespan, it is significant to many sectors of behavioral and social study, including education. Socioeconomic status, according to Ovute (2009), comprises elements including the family's monthly income, the parents' employment, the size of the family, and the parents' educational background. Gouc (2007) asserts that a family's socioeconomic standing is defined by their heritage, wealth, clout, and status in a particular culture.

In today's rapidly evolving global marketplace, understanding consumer behavior has become paramount for businesses seeking to thrive in a competitive environment. Consumer choices are driven by a complex interplay of factors, ranging from personal preferences and psychological influences to external socio-economic and demographic variables. Among these, socio-demographic profiles have emerged as crucial determinants that significantly shape the preferences, attitudes, and purchasing behaviors of individuals.

The socioeconomic situation of many people in our country now is a serious problem. A significant example of this is the growing cost of living, which makes life difficult for many Filipinos. The difficulties encountered in life have an effect on education. The level of education a person has influences their chances for success in life, their capacity for employment, and their general well-being, contend Battle and Lewis. Therefore, it is essential to comprehend the elements that promote or hinder academic success. People believe that education is essential to their life. According to Safaya, education is essential for healthy living and that without it, a person would be unsuited for group life. Academic achievement is of the utmost significance in a system of education where the intellectual development of persons is given priority.

Socio-demographic profiles encompass a rich tapestry of characteristics such as age, gender, income, education, occupation, ethnicity, family structure, and geographical location. These attributes provide a multifaceted lens through which researchers and marketers can gain valuable insights into consumer decision-making processes. By analyzing the socio-demographic dimensions of consumer behavior, businesses can tailor their marketing strategies, develop targeted products and services, and create engaging customer experiences that resonate with specific segments of the population.

The relevance of socio-demographic profiles in the study of consumer behavior is underscored by their pervasive influence on various aspects of purchasing decisions. For instance, age plays a significant role in determining product preferences, with different generations exhibiting distinct buying patterns. Gender differences often lead to varying consumption behaviors, with men and women exhibiting contrasting preferences for products, brands, and shopping channels. Income levels and socio-economic status not only affect purchasing power but also impact choices related to luxury items, everyday necessities, and expenditure on experiences. Educational attainment can influence the adoption of innovative technologies, while family structure and life stage determine consumption patterns, such as family-oriented or individual-centric buying decisions.

Moreover, the socio-demographic landscape is not static; it evolves over time due to societal shifts, cultural transformations, technological advancements, and economic fluctuations. The dynamic nature of socio-demographic profiles requires continuous research to capture emerging trends and changing consumer preferences. Understanding these fluctuations is essential for businesses to adapt and remain relevant to their target audiences.

This comprehensive exploration seeks to delve into the intricate connections between socio-demographic profiles and consumer behavior. By examining the existing body of knowledge and recent research findings, this study aims to shed light on the mechanisms through which socio-demographic variables shape consumer preferences, influence purchasing decisions, and drive market trends. Additionally, this research will examine the implications of socio-demographic analysis for businesses, marketing professionals, policymakers, and scholars, with a focus on how insights derived from such analysis can be translated into effective strategies that cater to diverse consumer segments.

Through an extensive review of literature and empirical studies, this investigation aims to provide a holistic understanding of the socio-demographic dimensions that underpin consumer behavior. By uncovering the nuances of how age, gender, income, education, family structure, and other socio-demographic factors intersect to mold consumer choices, this study seeks to equip stakeholders with actionable insights that can enhance their decision-making processes and contribute to more targeted and successful marketing endeavors.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The primary objective of this study was to ascertain the socioeconomic makeup of the Cagayan province's customers. It specifically aimed to respond to:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondent-consumers in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex
 - 1.2 marital status
 - 1.3 sectoral affiliation
 - 1.4 age
 - 1.5 highest educational attainment
 - 1.6 religious affiliation
 - 1.7 family size
 - 1.8 family income

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study made use of the descriptive-normative method of research employing the questionnaire as main data-gathering instrument. The researchers made use of structured questionnaires to gather the needed data which were given to the consumers. The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage. The respondents were chosen on the basis of sectoral representation which will provide a proportional representation of the consumers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Distribution of Participants in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
FEMALE	323	60.30
MALE	213	39.70
Total	536	100.00

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of participants in terms of sex. As shown in the table, three hundred and twenty-three (323) or 60.30 percent of the participants are females while two hundred and thirteen or 39.70 percent are males. According to a Bloomberg research, women account for over 85% of consumer purchases in the US and have a 95% overall power over the amount of products and services purchased. This number supports that assertion. A woman's buying habits are also profoundly rooted in her personality; they are literally written in her DNA. A woman will shop the same manner she does when she is 18 years old until she is 43 years old, according to a 2007 poll by the AMP Agency. It is an attitude of persistence. Women are given the authority that may contribute to closing the gender gap at the most fundamental levels of society while also strengthening society as a result. As a result, society gets stronger and women are given the ability to contribute to closing the gender gap at society's most fundamental levels. Additionally, it raises consumer awareness of their rights. The most popular college major for women is business, according to a recent review of the Department of Education's "Condition of Education 2009" by AAUW (previously known as the American Association of University Women). This only serves to clarify why, as seen by the numbers above, women make up the majority of respondents. This shows that the responses of female respondents may have been given more weight in the study's findings than those of male respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of Participants in terms of Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	294	54.90
Solo parent	16	3.00
Married	190	35.40
Widow/Widower	34	6.30
Legally Separated	2	0.40
Total	536	100.00

Table 2 indicates the frequency and percentage distribution of participants in terms of marital status. As shown in the table, majority of the participants are single with a frequency of two hundred and ninety-four (294) or 54.90 percent while the lowest frequency belongs to the legally separated with two (2) or .40 percent. The data imply that the immensity of the participants came from those who are single who are representing the youth sector of the study. The conclusion suggests that singles are more financially responsible for their purchases and decisions, which may increase interest in consumer awareness as they are responsible for the whole costs associated with their actions. ConsumersInternational.org study shows that single individuals try to lead busy lifestyles and fight feelings of loneliness. This might spark a number of marketing campaigns.

Table 3: Distribution of Participants in terms of Sector

Sector	Frequency	Percentage
Housewife	48	9.00
Farmers/fisher folks	49	9.10
Government/Private Employees	70	13.10
Persons with Disability	22	4.10
Business Sector	68	12.70
College/ High School Students	204	38.10
OSYs/ Unemployed	21	3.90
Senior Citizens	54	10.10
Total	536	100.00

The frequency and percentage distribution of participants in terms of sector is shown in Table 3. As shown in the table, the High School/College students have the highest frequency of two hundred and four (204) or 38.10 percent while the least sector with a frequency of twenty-one (21) or 3.90 belongs to the OSYs/Unemployed. The data above showed that all of the significant sectors were represented in the conduct of this study.

Table 4: Distribution of Participants in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
10-18 years old (youth)	139	25.90
19-59 years old (middle age)	324	60.40
60 years old and above (old)	73	13.70
Total	536	100.00

Age of the participants is one of the most important characteristics in understanding their views about a particular problem which may indicate the level of maturity of a person. The frequency and percentage distribution of participants in terms of age is shown in table 4. As indicated in the table, the participants in the middle age (19-59 years old) have the highest frequency of three hundred and twenty-four (324) or 60.40 percent. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, of the 108.67 million households in the country, 33.4 million, or 30.70% of the total household population, were under the age of 15, 69.40 million, or 63.90%, were between the ages of 15 and 64, and 5.86 million, or 5.40%, were 65 and older.

Table 5: Distribution of Participants in terms of Education

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Level	27	5.00
Elementary Graduate	168	31.30
High School Level	86	16.00
High School Graduate	37	6.90
Bachelor Level	10	1.90
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	27	5.00
Graduate Level	70	13.10
Completed Graduate Studies	82	15.30
Technical/Vocational	29	5.40
Total	536	100.00

Education is one of the most important spheres that can affect the person’s attitudes and the way of looking and understanding any particular social phenomenon. Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of participants in terms of highest educational attainment. As revealed in the table, elementary graduate has the highest frequency of one hundred and sixty-eight (168) or 31.30 percent while the lowest frequency of ten (10) or 1.90 percent belongs to bachelor’s level. These results showed that all the participants have entered formal school thus capacitating them the ability to know their rights as consumers but confirm an article about poverty in the Philippines depicting that majority of Filipino households have only achieved basic levels of education. The findings of the study by Mittal, I., and Gupta (2013) contradict this conclusion. found that respondents with better education and income levels had greater knowledge than respondents with less education and income levels. It was unexpected to learn that despite broad knowledge of consumer rights, they weren't being effectively exercised.

Table 6: Distribution of Participants in terms of Religious Affiliation

Religious Affiliation	Frequency	Percentage
Roman Catholic	419	78.20
Iglesia ni Cristo	14	2.60
Jehovah’s Witnesses	18	3.40
Protestant	9	1.70
Evangelical	2	.40
Born-Again Christian	36	6.70
Islam	1	.20
JIL Movement	1	.20
Seventh Day Adventist	1	.20
Baptist	6	1.10
Others (pls. specify)	29	5.40
<i>Atheist</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>Church of Christ</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>1.70</i>
<i>Church of Christ the King</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>Crusaders</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>EUCF</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>Four Square Gospel Church</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>IFI</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>.60</i>
<i>Kingdom of Christ</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>Lutheran Church</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
<i>Methodist</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>.90</i>
<i>Latter Day Saints</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>.70</i>
<i>Presbyterian</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>.20</i>
Total	536	100.00

The religious affiliation of the participants is shown in table 6. As shown in the table, majority of the participants belong to the Roman Catholic with a frequency of four hundred and nineteen (419) or 78.20 percent while the lowest frequency of one (1) or .20 percent belong to JIL, Islam and seventh Day Adventist. This implies that Roman Catholic is still the predominant religion in the country which is attributable to the three centuries of Spanish colonization of the country. This

implies that Roman Catholicism is still the most common religion in the nation despite the three centuries of Spanish occupation. The finding is supported by a Stanford University poll that determined that an estimated 80.9 percent of Filipinos identify as Roman Catholics and by a Center for Global Education article on religion in the Philippines. The assertion that more than 86 percent of the population is Roman Catholic is supported by both a Center for Global Education article about religion in the Philippines and a Stanford University study, which calculates that 80.9% of Filipinos identify as Roman Catholic.

Table 7: Distribution of Participants in terms of Family Size

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage
less than 4	106	19.80
4-6	323	60.30
7 and up	107	20.00
Total	536	100.00

The size of the family is an important determinant that affects a person's values, beliefs and behavior and consequently may influence his attitudes towards a particular problem. Table 7 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants in terms of their family size. As reflected in the table, majority of the participants belonged to the medium-sized family of 4-6 members with a frequency of three hundred and twenty-three (323) or 60.30 percent, an indication that majority of the participants are very much conscious of the attached advantage of a few numbers of family members.

Table 8: Distribution of Participants in terms of Monthly Family Income

Monthly Family Income	Frequency	Percentage
30,000 and below	416	77.60
30,001-60,000	78	14.60
60,001-90,000	24	4.50
90,001-120,000	6	1.10
120,001 and above	12	2.20
Total	536	100.00

Income is one of the most important material resources of the family and plays an important role in shaping the economic conditions of an individual which in turn is likely to have bearing on his dispositions about issues confronting him. It is evident from Table 8 that majority of the participants with a frequency of four hundred and sixteen (416) or 77.60 percent are earning 30,000 or below in a month, an indication that majority of the participants are below the poverty threshold showing the minimum income necessary to meet basic food and non-food needs for an average family. The results are in line with a survey conducted by Statista between 2012 and 2021 that looked at the average family income in the Philippines. The findings show that, as of the first half of that time period, the average family income in the Philippines was 149.98 thousand pesos, or around P25,000.00 per month.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

From the results of the study, the following findings are founded

1. Distribution of participants in terms of sex – Female respondents outnumbered the male respondents wherein 60.30% are female while only 39.70% are male.
2. Marital status - Majority of the participants are single with a frequency of 294 while the lowest frequency belongs to the legally separated with 2.
3. Distribution of participants in terms of sector - the High School/College students have the highest frequency of 204 while the least sector with a frequency of 21 belongs to the OSYs/Unemployed.
4. Distribution of participants in terms of age - the participants in the middle age (19-59 years old) have the highest frequency of 324 while participants in the old age (60 years old and above) have the lowest frequency of 73.
5. Distribution of participants in terms of education - Elementary graduate has the highest frequency of 168 while the lowest frequency of 10 belongs to bachelor's level.
6. Distribution of participants in terms of religious affiliation - Majority of the participants belong to the Roman Catholic with a frequency of 419 while the lowest frequency of 1 belongs to JIL, Islam and seventh Day Adventist.
7. Distribution of participants in terms of family size - Medium-sized family of 4-6 members has the highest frequency of 323 while the lowest frequency of 106 belong to a family size of less than 4.
8. Distribution of participants in terms of monthly family income - Majority of the participants with a frequency of 416 are earning 30,000 or below in a month while the lowest frequency of 6 are earning 90,0001 – 120,000.

CONCLUSIONS

Based from the research conducted, conclusions were realized where the family monthly income of majority of the student-respondents is below the poverty line based on National Economic Development Authority bulletin. The family size falls under the average family size in the Philippines which is 4 – 6 members. From the different significant sectors under study, majority of the consumer respondents belong to the college/high school students. Majority of the consumer-respondents fall in the middle age (19-59 years old). Majority of the consumer-respondents are Roman Catholic. Majority of the respondents are elementary graduate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the foregoing findings, the researchers have the following recommendations to offer:

1. Additional studies should be conducted to determine other variables and make use of more respondents to strengthen the results.
2. Employ other important variables to determine the socio-demographic status of the respondents that would enhance the results.

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